

ON THE RELATION BETWEEN THE STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL CHELATES IN SOLUTION AND THE ELECTRO-NEGATIVITY OF THEIR METAL COMPONENTS

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The relation between the stability constants of metal chelates of doubly charged ions of Mn, Fe, Co, Ni and Cu in solution and their electronegativity has been discussed from thermodynamical consideration. A simple linear relation existing between $\sqrt{\log K_1}$ and χ has been postulated where K_1 is the first stability constant and χ , the 'selected' Gordy and Thomas electronegativity.

Several workers have tried to relate the values of $\log K_1$ (where K_1 is the first stability constant of a metal chelate in solution) of the chelates of a series of metal ions with a given ligand with the fundamental properties of metal ions like ionisation potentials, electronegativity, ionic radius, etc. When the chelates formed by the doubly charged ions of Mn, Fe, Co, Ni and Cu, the $\log K_1$ values of which conform to Irving-Williams' order (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3192) in a large number of cases, are considered, the relations suggested so far reduce to the following:

(i). Linear correlation of $\log K_1$ with the sum of the first and second ionisation potentials of the gaseous atoms, corresponding to the change, $M \rightarrow M^{2+} + 2e$, viz., $I_1 + I_2$ (Irving and Williams, *Nature*, 1948, 162, 746; Ackermann *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1949, 163, 723).

(ii). Linear correlation with I_2 , corresponding to the change, $M^+ \rightarrow M^{2+} + e$ (Calvin and Melchior, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, 70, 3270).

(iii). Straight line plot of $\log K_1$ against χ , where χ is the Haissinsky electronegativity (* *J. Phys. Radium*, 1946, 7, 7) of the bivalent metal M^{2+} (* Van Uitert *et al.*, Paper VII, Chelate Compound Stabilities in the Dissolved State, Report NYO-3372, March 5, 1952).

(iv). Smooth plot of $\log K_1$ against χ (Chapman, *Nature*, 1954, 174, 887).

Figs. 1, 2 and 3 show the results of application of these relations to a few data drawn from Martell and Calvin ("Chemistry of the Metal Chelate Compounds", New York, Prentice-Hall, Inc., 1952). $I_1 + I_2$ and I_2 are expressed in kcal., the necessary data being taken from Williams (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1951, 55, 123, Table II) and Latimer ("The Oxidation States of the Elements and their Potentials in Aqueous Solutions", 2nd ed., New York, Prentice-Hall, Inc., 1952) respectively. The electronegativities used are the "selected" values of Gordy and Thomas (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1956, 24, 439), which are in general agreement with the Haissinsky values (*loc. cit.*). For Fe only, the Haissinsky value 1.65 has been used so that the corresponding points do not overlap those for Co. It is seen that relation (i) yields the best straight lines, while no definite relation between $\log K_1$ and χ arises.

* The original papers were not consulted.

FIG. 2

FIG. 1

FIG. 3

At the present state of our knowledge of chemical bonding, it is difficult to say which of the two properties, viz., ionisation potential or electronegativity of an atom, is more significant in this respect. Although ionisation potential is related to electronegativity by Mulliken's definition of electronegativity as $\chi = (I + E)/2$, where I is the ionisation potential and E , the electron affinity of the atom, the ionisation potential involved in this definition refers to the ionisation potential of the particular "valence state" of the atom, a quantity difficult to calculate and relation of which with the ionisation potential of the gaseous atom is not clearly known. However, electronegativity is related, at least semi-quantitatively, in the case of simple compounds to bond polarity, heat of formation etc., as shown by the classical work of Pauling. A definite relation between $\log K_1$ and χ would therefore be of great interest.

The reaction between a metal ion M and a ligand L , e.g., the anion of a chelating acid or an amine, in a solution consists of the displacement of the solvation sheath around the metal ion followed by bond formation between the metal ion and the ligand. $\log K$ of such a reaction, e.g.,

(where n and p are the numbers of water molecules, and charges are omitted for generality), measures the standard free energy of the reaction in view of the thermodynamic relation

$$\Delta F^\circ = -RT \ln K.$$

Now

$$\Delta F^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T \Delta S^\circ.$$

If the increase of entropy in a reaction is regarded as a measure of the resultant increase in "disorder" and if the suggestion of Frank and Evans (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1945, 13, 507) that the ions in an aqueous solution order the water molecules around them so as to form an "ice-berg" is accepted, it will be seen that for the reactions of a series of metal ions with the same ligand under the same conditions, the variations in the ΔS° values will be determined by the variations in the entropy change involved in the removal of the hydration sheath. For ions of the same charge and varying little in radius and atomic weight, like the doubly charged ions of Mn, Fe, Co, Ni and Cu, these entropy changes may be regarded as more or less the same, as seen from the equation of Powell and Latimer (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1951, 19, 1139) for the entropies of monoatomic ions in aqueous solution. Log K values then become a measure of the ΔH° values. The heat of formation of a gaseous molecule containing only single bonds and formed from the elements in their standard states, is given roughly according to Pauling ("The Nature of the Chemical Bond", 2nd ed., Ithaca, Cornell University Press, 1945, p. 62) by

$$Q_{\text{form.}} = 23.06 \sum (\chi_A - \chi_B)^2 - 55.1 n_N - 24.2 n_O$$

where χ_A and χ_B are the electronegativities of the atoms between which a single bond is formed, and n_N and n_O are the numbers of atoms of nitrogen and oxygen in the molecule. Now the ΔH° values consist of heat changes involved in the removal of the solvation sheath and formation of the metal—ligand bond. For the series considered here, the variable factor in both the heat terms is the metal ion only. It is therefore possible that in view of the Pauling relation $\sqrt{\log K_1}$ would bear a linear relation with χ , the electronegativity of the metal. This is shown to be true (Fig. 4) of the ligands considered in Figs. 1, 2 and 3, except for the values corresponding to Fe.

Comparison of Figs. 1 and 4 shows that the $\sqrt{\log K_1}$ against χ -plot yields straight lines which are as good as those obtained in the $\log K_1$ against $(I_1 + I_2)$ plot, if the points for Fe are excluded. In view of the uncertainties in the data it is difficult to say which of these two relations is the better one. If both are assumed to be equally true, a simple relation between χ^2 and $(I_1 + I_2)$ may be expected for the series of elements considered. Fig. 5 shows this to be linear, the value for Fe being again an exception. It is interesting to note that if the value $\chi = 1.57$ is chosen for Feⁿ, not only does it fall on the χ^2 against $I_1 + I_2$ plot, but the $\log K_1$ values for Fe also fall on the $\sqrt{\log K_1}$ against χ -plot.

The relation given here has been derived on a qualitative basis. It is realised that whereas the relation between Q and χ , as used here, applies to the reaction

FIG. 4

FIG. 5

$\log K_1$ values refer to the corresponding reaction in solution. The thermochemical relations between the changes in heat content in the two reactions and other details will be published later.

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